

Comparative Analysis of MgB₂ Cable Layouts for 1 GW Superconducting Transmission - Insights from the SCARLET Project

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Abstract—The European project SCARLET is dedicated to advancing the integration and application of superconducting technologies for medium voltage direct current (MVDC) systems. One of the main innovations within SCARLET is the development of a dual-purpose infrastructure that combines the transmission of bulk electricity and liquid hydrogen. The MgB₂ superconducting cable, operating at around 20 K, finds its suitable environment within the pipeline for liquid hydrogen transport. This integration promises a compact and economically attractive solution for the simultaneous distribution of hydrogen and electricity. In this paper, we present various designs of the MgB₂ cable core, showcasing results from electro-thermal simulations and highlighting the strengths and potential challenges. The intent of this work is to help identify the most effective cable configuration that meets the requirements of energy efficiency and compactness, while also considering the constraints associated with the production phase. In addition, to enhance the sensitivity to the thermal behaviour, a thermal model was developed and presented.

Index Terms—MVDC Cables, MgB₂ cable, Superconductivity, Liquid Hydrogen, Hybrid Power Transmission, Cable Modelling, Electro-Thermal Modelling, SCARLET.

I. INTRODUCTION

SUPERCONDUCTING technologies have made significant advancements, reaching a level where they are now practical for high-current applications, crucial for modern power transmission networks. These advances are particularly relevant in the development of cables that can transmit electricity over long distances with minimal losses in AC and no losses in DC. High-Temperature Superconductors (HTS), like magnesium diboride (MgB₂) or Rare-earth Barium Copper Oxide family (ReBCO), offer unique opportunities for improving the efficiency and capacity of power transmission.

The EU Green Deal emphasizes hydrogen's expanding role as an energy vector, with initiatives aimed at establishing production hubs and pipeline networks [1]. Given this backdrop,

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement 101075602, by the European Union - NextGenerationEU, in the framework of the NEST (Network 4 Energy Sustainable Transition) SPOKE 7 and ECOSISTER SPOKE 4, PNRR - M4C2 - I1.3. The views and opinions expressed are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, nor can the European Union be held responsible for them. (Corresponding author: francesco.mimmi2@unibo.it)

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developing efficient hydrogen transmission systems is crucial for supplying power plants, industries, and transportation centers that also demand high electric power. The integration of MgB₂ cables within hydrogen pipelines addresses these needs by offering a compact, cost-effective solution for simultaneous electricity and hydrogen transport. This dual functionality is particularly beneficial for regions where renewable energy sources are far from consumption centres, enhancing the potential of this synergic hybrid transmission system.

The concept of hybrid transmission systems was first proposed by Paul Michael Grant in 2004 [2], [3], represented as a highly efficient and cost-effective method for energy distribution. Moreover, employing liquid hydrogen both as a coolant and as an energy vector has the potential to revolutionize long-distance power grids.

The first successful prototype of such a hybrid energy transfer system was developed and tested in 2013 using a 10 meter-long MgB₂ cable [4], with further advancements following in subsequent years with a 30 meters long cable [5].

Two other projects of extreme relevance that represent milestones for MgB₂ cables' technology are the *Superconducting Link* for the LHC upgrade at CERN [6]–[8] and *Best Paths* Project [9]–[11]. The first one established an innovative electrical transfer line to power the HL-LHC inner triplet magnets, comprising 100-meter SC-Links cooled by forced helium gas flow, operating at 25 K to deliver 120 kA in DC. The latter is a significant EU-funded project, aimed to validate high-voltage direct-current (HVDC) superconducting links, culminating in the first demonstration of a 3GW class superconducting cable system operating at 320 kV and 10 kA in helium gas. The LHC Superconducting Link is composed of concentric cables bundled together within a single cryostat. These cables form multiple circuits that deliver current to and from various magnets. In other words, the SC Link is essentially a grouping of several power supply circuits, achieving a total current-carrying capacity of 120 kA. The Best Path cable is a unique transmission cable, operating at much higher voltage and hence, requiring to carry much less current. It is essentially just a single concentric cable like those used in the SC link, with the corresponding number of wires in order to address the current capacity of 10 kA at 20 K.

None of the pilots addressed the transmission of bulk power of the order of 1 GW under medium voltage and over long distances (10 to 100 km), cooled by liquid hydrogen. This is exactly where the SCARLET project is positioned, namely to

Fig. 1. MgB₂ Wire1 (D = 1.33 mm) performance used for the simulations. Solid markers represent values directly measured by ASG Superconductors, whereas open markers are derived through linear extrapolation.

deploy a full-scale MgB₂-based cable system cooled by LH₂ for a 1 GW bipolar link (± 25 kV / 20 kA). This system will enable the simultaneous transmission of two independent energy vectors, electricity and hydrogen, offering new opportunities for energy storage and distribution. This innovative approach is expected to significantly improve energy efficiency and reduce operational costs, marking a new era in power transmission technology.

A preliminary study, conducted within the SCARLET project, focused on a 500 MW DC monopolar cable transferring 20 kA at 25 kV, while distributing LH₂ in a temperature range from 20 K - 25 K [12]. The study laid the groundwork for optimizing cable designs that meet the operational demands of the energy sector while remaining feasible and cost-effective for industrial production.

In this article, we present three different layouts of 500 MW/20 kA DC MgB₂ monopoles, operating in liquid hydrogen at 23 K. The structure of the article is organized as follows: Section II explores three distinct cable layouts; Section III presents a scenario that includes both electrical and hydrogen loads with a pole-to-pole fault; Section IV introduces the developed thermo-electric model; and Section V examines and compares the performance of the three cables' layout during transient energization and fault conditions.

II. CABLE DESIGN

In the design of a superconducting cable, the first crucial step is selecting the type of MgB₂ wire to be used.

Several production techniques exist for manufacturing MgB₂ wires [13]. The most common methods include the Powder-in-Tube (PIT) method [14], the Internal Magnesium Diffusion (IMD) process [15]–[17], and the more recent Advanced Internal Magnesium Infiltration (AIMI) technique [18]. The latter two methods, IMD and AIMI, are intrinsically *in-situ* methods, which allow to improve the critical current den-

sity J_c for high magnetic field applications, but this enhancement comes at the cost of making the material more fragile and less resistant to mechanical stresses. Because of their mechanical fragility, wires produced with these techniques are unsuitable for cabling processes in long-length cable applications. In contrast, the Powder-in-Tube (PIT) technique is well-known and deeply industrialized. The PIT method further divided into *ex-situ* and *in-situ* approaches. While the *ex-situ* method uses *fully reacted* MgB₂ powders, the *in-situ* method utilizes a mixture of *unreacted* magnesium (Mg) and boron (B). Wires produced with the *in-situ* technique need a final heat treatment that embrittles the wires [19]; moreover, the final heat treatment can occur only for short-length objects. The *in-situ* technique is hence not compatible with long-length cables envisioned for power transmission. On the other hand, the *ex-situ* technique allows for better control over the powder's granulometry and degree of purity. Moreover, it results in more robust conductors, already reacted MgB₂ superconductors that are still mechanically flexible, making wires readily employed for cabling operations. For these reasons, the *ex-situ* PIT method has proven to be the most suitable for the development of long conductors and complex multifilamentary wire geometries.

ASG Superconductors employs the technique of *ex-situ* PIT to produce MgB₂ multifilamentary wires, which are commercially available in long lengths [20].

Different wires have been used in various cable projects. The first hybrid energy prototype in Russia used the MgB₂ tape (the so-called *MRO tape*) [4] because, at that time, it was the only industrially available *ex-situ* tape produced by ASG Superconductors. For the Superconducting Link at CERN, ASG Superconductors developed for the first time a MgB₂ round wire, called *Wire 2* [6], [7]. For the Best Path project, a further development of the round wire was pursued, producing *Wire 1*, with a higher critical current due to a higher MgB₂ fraction in the wire [9], [10], [21], [22]. For these reasons, *Wire 1*, the same used in the Best Paths project, was also chosen for the Scarlet project, in all three layouts.

The results presented in Section V were obtained considering the critical current values (I_c) shown in Figure 1. Specifically, ASG Superconductors provided the measurement data, represented by solid markers, and labeled as *Meas* (Measured), while open markers correspond to values of I_c obtained through linear extrapolation, labeled as *Extr* (Extrapolated).

After defining the MgB₂ wire's performance characteristics, we determine the required number of superconducting wires for each cable configuration. Each monopole must carry 20 kA, but the number of wires varies depending on further constraints. The first two constraints are the safety factor $I/I_c = 0.75$ at 23 K, and the maximum diameter of the monopole, which according to the Scarlet guidelines, should be around 25 mm. The chosen diameter affects the magnetic field acting on the wires and may affect the current distribution in multilayer layouts. In a more compact arrangement, the MgB₂ wires will be subjected to a higher magnetic field density B , reducing the wires' performance.

To clarify the upcoming explanations, we introduce the terminology for the elements that can compose the active part

Fig. 2. Cross-section of a concentric cable core with a diameter of 8.4 mm, comprising two layers of MgB_2 wires (48 wires in total) and two layers of copper bundles plus a central bundle, totaling 19 copper bundles. The figure has been taken from [7], as it shows a section of a cable constituting the LHC SC Link, and its layout is also suitable for the cable in Figure 3c.

of a cable, also referred to as the *Core*.

Figure 2 shows the cross-section of a concentric cable core, highlighting its constituent components, which will be referenced in the following explanations. In the example of Figure 2, the core consists of two layers of MgB_2 wires and two layers of copper bundles plus a central copper bundle. Each MgB_2 layer contains a specific number of MgB_2 wires (Wire 1 with a diameter of 1.33 mm), and each wire is composed by 36 MgB_2 filaments (with a diameter of around 0.1 mm), embedded in a matrix of Monel and Nickel.

The central copper part serves as the *former*. The former is a copper rope composed of multiple copper bundles, arranged in two layers plus a central bundle. Each copper bundle, in turn, consists of several fine copper wires used for ultra-flexible copper cables.

We chose to use copper bundles instead of bulk copper wires to increase the copper filling factor and to address the issue of bending forces due to the twisting of the bundles. If the copper bundles were made of a single bulk conductor, torsional forces would cause the cable to bend. By using copper bundles, the thin internal copper wires are free to slide relative to each other. This design choice, along with the use of detorsion cabling machines, helps prevent the generation of torsional forces caused by twisting and reduces the overall stiffness of the cable.

In the following models, each copper bundle will be treated and represented not by all its individual copper wires, but as a single bulk copper conductor.

A. Concentric Two Layers 42 MgB_2 Wires

This layout, shown in Figure 3c (referring also to Figure 2 for the core), consists of 2 layers with 18 and 24 MgB_2 wires respectively. It was designed to be "*fault tolerant*", it means that it entails a controlled transition of the cable from the

Fig. 3. MgB_2 cable layouts. In descending order of diameter from left to the right: (a) Concentric One Layer 36 MgB_2 Wires; (b) Rope-Strand 6 Petals 48 MgB_2 Wires; (c) Concentric Two Layers 42 MgB_2 Wires.

superconducting state to the normal resistive state during the fault. The safety factor is calculated at 23 K by means of Equation (1). This takes into account the magnetic field on the wires that is 0.4 T on the inner layers and 0.75 T on the outer one. Extracting the I_c of the wires from Figure 1, we obtain:

$$\frac{I}{I_c} = \frac{20000A}{828A \cdot 18 + 579A \cdot 24} = 0.70 \quad (1)$$

That is a quite wide current's margin so as the number of MgB_2 wires allows for an overcurrent during a limited time without damage to the conductor and its insulation. The superconducting wires are arranged in two concentric layers to meet the maximum diameter constrain. The cable layout is composed by the following components:

- **Former:** the former represent central copper rope made up by 19 copper bundles, with a diameter of 1.4 mm, arranged in 2 layers plus the central copper bundle (1+6+12).

- **MgB₂ 1:** inner layer composed by 18 MgB₂ wires.
- **MgB₂ 2:** outer layer composed by 24 MgB₂ wires.
- **Shield:** It gathers all 23 copper tapes that make up the cable's shield.

With a total diameter of the cable is $D = 20.55$ mm, this is the most compact configuration.

In Section V, simulation results will show that this layout leads to a non-uniform current distributions across the two layers during transients, reducing the overall efficiency of the cable and failing to fully optimize the use of all the MgB₂ wires. The reason lies in the fact that the two MgB₂ layers are arranged at different radii, resulting in the linkage of different magnetic fluxes. In fact, since we are dealing with superconductors, where resistance is zero, the current distribution will be dominated by the reactance due to the inductance of the conductors. As a result, a different design has been studied.

B. Concentric One Layer 36 MgB₂ Wires

To address the issue of current non-uniformity, all MgB₂ wires must be linked to the same magnetic field, ensuring they are magnetically equivalent. For this reason all the superconducting wires must be arranged in a single layer, but the number of superconducting wires is limited by a technical constrain in the manufacturing process. Currently, the companies involved do not have cabling machines capable of arranging more than 36 wires in a single layer. As a result, 36 wires represent the maximum number of superconducting wires that can be positioned in one layer. Even though the number of superconducting wires is fewer than in the two-layer configuration, the diameter is larger, resulting in each wire experiencing a reduced magnetic field of 0.5 T. Referring to Figure 1, the I_c at 0.5 T and 23 K is 752 A for each wire. Therefore, the safety factor is:

$$\frac{I}{I_c} = \frac{20000A}{752A \cdot 36} = 0.74 \quad (2)$$

So the current's margin is however acceptable to design a *fault tolerant* cable. The conductive parts of this cable have been grouped as following:

- **Former:** the former represent central copper rope made up by 61 small copper bundles, of equivalent diameter of 1.7 mm, arranged in 4 layers plus the central copper bundle (1+6+12+18+24).
- **MgB₂:** It gathers all 36 MgB₂ wires arranged in a single circular layer.
- **Shield:** It gathers all 29 copper tapes that make up the cable's shield.

The total diameter of the cable is $D = 26.08$ mm. Although the diameter slightly exceeds 25 mm, it is still acceptable because it does not change the cable's function nor does it alter the cable's footprint within the cryostat. Furthermore, this layout is the simplest to manufacture and provides a uniform current distribution, as reported in Section V.

C. Rope-Strand 6 Petals 48 MgB₂ Wires

The third proposed design investigate the behavior of a "fault transparent" cable. Fault transparent superconducting

cables are designed to maintain their superconducting properties and continue operation even in the presence of faults, without developing any increasing in resistance. Due to this characteristic, the cable does not contribute to limiting the fault current while the breakers are interrupting the circuit. The *Rope-Strand 6 Petals with 48 MgB₂ Wires* layout enables the arrangement of more wires while maintaining a compact radius that meets Scarlet's specifications. From the constitutive point of view, this layout has already been successfully implemented in the superconducting link for the High Luminosity of the LHC [5], [9]. The layout allows to accommodate a greater number of superconducting wires. The resulting magnetic field on the wires is about 0.65 T which, considering the graph in Figure 1 once again, leads to a critical current at 23 K of each wire of 643 A. The safety factor is hence determined as follows:

$$\frac{I}{I_c} = \frac{20000A}{643A \cdot 48} = 0.65 \quad (3)$$

This safety factor enables the cable to be *fault transparent*.

The Rope-Strand Cable is composed of different parts:

- **Former:** The former represent the concentric copper rope made up of 19 bundles, with a diameter of 0.8 mm, grouped into 2 layers plus the central copper bundle (1+6+12).
- **Petals:** with petals, we refer to the 6 outer ropes that twist around the concentric copper bundle. Each petal (or rope) is composed by:
 - **Petal Core:** copper bundle at the centre of each petal, with a diameter of 2.5 mm.
 - **MgB₂:** 8 MgB₂ wires arranged around each petal core and twisting around them. The total MgB₂ wires are $8 \times 6 = 48$.
 - **Shield:** It gathers the 27 copper tapes that make up the cable's shield.

The MgB₂ wires have a *double twisting*: they twist around the axis of each petal core, which are then wrapped with opposite twist direction and different pitch length around the axis of the cable. This cable layout is *completely transposed*. Each MgB₂ wire of a petal will experience all positions around the petal core, making all the MgB₂ wires perfectly equivalent in terms of electromagnetic perspective. The total diameter of the cable is $D = 23.48$ mm.

III. CASE STUDY

The identified application is depicted in Figure 4, where 2×500 MW DC Monopolar cable system is designed to transfer 1 GW while distributing liquid hydrogen to three main aggregated loads: the first is a port including the port area, auxiliary services, and a fleet of ships; the second is a steel foundry; and the third is a fleet of ground vehicles.

Each load requires both electrical power and hydrogen. The mass flow rate of hydrogen is of 10 t/h (5 t/h inside each pipe).

The transport configuration is of two monopoles and two hydrogen pipes, so each monopole is inside its own hydrogen pipe. As an example, in Figure 5 is reported the 2D section and 3D view of a monopole, with concentric layout, inside one hydrogen pipe, transporting a mass flow rate of 1.39 kg/s

Fig. 4. Schematic of the electric power and liquid hydrogen transmission system supplying a port, an industry and a fleet of land vehicles. The pole-to-pole fault is located just outside the cable's termination, near the loads.

Fig. 5. Layout of a single monopole inside the cryostat for the concentric One Layer 36 MgB₂ Wires cable. (a) 2D section; (b) 3D view.

as reported in Table I. All data reported in Table I, II and III have been computed with the CoolProp Library [23]. Since the liquid hydrogen has an energy density of 120 MJ/kg, such a transmission system is hence capable to transport 1000 MW of electric power and 330 MW of chemical energy.

In this article, we discuss the worst-case scenario for a fault occurring *external* to the cable. It is crucial to highlight the term *external*, as this type of fault does not disrupt the cable, allowing for normal operations to resume once the fault is cleared. These simulations has been considered to investigate the cable's response to increased current resulting from an external short circuit and to determine the time recovery it takes to resume service.

TABLE I
PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND PARAMETERS OF LIQUID HYDROGEN AT
TEMPERATURE $T = 23$ K AND PRESSURE $P = 10$ BAR

Property	Symbol	Value	Unit (SI)
Mass Density	ρ	$6.894 \times 10^{+1}$	kg/m ³
Thermal Conductivity	k_{th}	1.053×10^{-1}	W/m/K
Specific Heat Capacity	c_p	$1.085 \times 10^{+4}$	J/kg/K
Dynamic Viscosity	μ	1.175×10^{-5}	Pa·s

IV. ELECTROTHERMAL MODELS OF THE MGB2 CABLE LAYOUTS

In this section, the electro-thermal model implemented in Simulink will be described. First, we need to address some practical issues that have arisen.

The formers of all three cables are subjected to compression during the production phase, which reduces their overall diameter while increasing the filling factor. This leads to two main effects: first, an increase in the contact surface between each copper wire, resulting in enhanced thermal conductivity; and second, an overall reduction in diameter. In Figure 3, the 3D and 2D cross-sections are shown, where the formers are depicted without compression. However, the diameter of each copper bundle has been reduced to take into account the effect of compression and, more in particular, to obtain the correct former's outer diameter and the actual path of the copper bundles and MgB₂ wires. The definition of the correct geometry and position of the wires is crucial for the calculations of the magnetic field and the magnetic coupling coefficients. Therefore, both the calculations of magnetic field density and the inductance between each conductor have been carried out considering the compressed geometry.

On the other hand, for the electro-thermal parameters, compression has been ignored because mass conservation is the most important factor, and considering compression would correspond to smaller conductors' volumes. Therefore, the uncompressed geometry was considered to obtain the correct values of total electrical resistance, thermal capacity, and thermal conductivity.

A. Electrical Model

For the electrical model, refer to Figure 6, where each layer is modeled as a bulk ring conductor, electrically isolated from the others, given that all conductors within a layer are exposed to the same magnetic field. In fact, each conductor or bundle in one layer is positioned at the same distance from the centre and is twisted. This means that each conductor will occupy all positions of the others in the same layer, rendering them electromagnetically identical. This property allows us to assume that each conductor carries the same current as the others in the same layer. Therefore, we can model all conductors in each layer as a single bulk annular conductor with uniformly distributed current, ensuring an accurate representation. This reduction procedure is applied to all three layouts and assumes that all conductors of the same cable layer (former layer, MgB₂ layer, shield layer, etc.) carry the same current and operate at the same temperature. Therefore, the resistive voltage drop is the same for all conductors of the same layer. Based on this assumption, all conductors of one layer can be merged into a single conductor whereby the current follows a helical path. This procedure has been thoroughly described in [24].

Focusing on the *Rope bundle* layout of Section II-C, each petal is positioned at the same distance from the centre and is twisted. This means that each petal will occupy all positions that the other petals do, rendering each petal electromagnetically identical. This property allows us to assume that all petals carry the same current. Furthermore, since the MgB₂ wires of

Fig. 6. Schematic view of the cables' model after the reduction procedure, treating all the conductors in a layer as a unique bulk conductor. (a) Concentric One Layer 36 MgB_2 wires; (b) Rope-Strand 6 Petals 48 MgB_2 Wires; (c) Concentric Two Layers 42 MgB_2 Wires.

each petal twist around its own petal core, they will experience all positions of the other wires within the same petal, making them equivalent from an electromagnetic perspective. So it is reasonable to assume that all the 48 MgB_2 wires carry the same current since each wire experiences all the positions of all the others. This allows us to model all the 48 MgB_2 wires as a single bulk annular conductor, carrying a uniformly distributed current, as depicted in Figure 6b. Note that the purpose of this figure is not to show the actual geometry considered in the model but rather to provide a schematic view of the cable model after applying the reduction procedure. It illustrates how the wires have been grouped together to form single bulk conductors.

All the self- and mutual-induction coefficients of the layered conductors, as well as their resistances, are obtained starting from the calculation of the parameters of the *individual* conductors following the approach explained in [24].

B. Thermal Model

The thermal model is implemented using the thermal blocks from the Simscape Multiphysics library. For an in-depth analysis of an alternative thermal implementation via the Mellor network approach, please refer to the article [25].

The thermal model of the cable relies on numerous assumptions due to the presence of composite materials, varying sizes and shapes, and the refrigerant fluid whose dynamics within the cable are not fully known. No measurements have yet been made to thermally characterize all parts of the cable and the thermal conduction phenomena occurring within it. Due to these numerous unknowns, the values, derived from the analysis reported in this article, are not expected to be final, but the

Fig. 7. Thermal model of each MgB_2 cable layout (half 2D section view). Red row identifies thermal conduction, whereas double yellow rows identify thermal convection with liquid hydrogen. (a) Concentric One Layer 36 MgB_2 wires; (b) Rope-Strand 6 Petals 48 MgB_2 Wires; (c) Concentric Two Layers 42 MgB_2 Wires.

Fig. 8. Left: Cross-sectional view of a sample MgB_2 cable used in the LHC Superconducting Link. Right: Detailed view of the thermal contacts between a single MgB_2 wire with carbon black, former, adjacent wires and liquid hydrogen.

goal is to provide a good estimation for these heat exchange phenomena, facilitating the preliminary understanding.

The *reduction* approach used for the electrical model has also been applied to the thermal model. Each layer of the cable is treated as a single material with its own thermal mass. All conductors within the same layer are assumed to have the same temperature at all times. Each layer exchanges heat either through convection with the hydrogen or through conduction with adjacent layers. These assumptions regarding heat exchange are outlined in Figure 7 where, at first glance, it is possible to notice a different former's geometry from the electrical model in Figure 6. In the electrical model, it was decided to divide the former into layers to model the skin effect and achieve a more accurate current distribution. However, in the thermal model, the former is modeled as a single conductor because it is compacted and the thermal conductivity of copper is extremely high. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that all conductors within the former will almost instantaneously reach the same temperature. This assumption is supported by Figure 8, which displays the core of one of the concentric MgB_2 cables employed in the LHC Superconducting Link,

demonstrates how the former is fully compacted. The design shown in Figure 8 is very similar to that of one layer of 36 MgB₂ wires for SCARLET project in Figure 3a and, for this reason, we discuss here the assumptions made with this cable layout. However, the same procedure has been implemented to derive the parameters for the other two cable's layout.

In characterizing the thermal behaviour of the cable, it is needed to divide the cable environment into two sub-environments:

- *Outside the cable*: External to the shield, hydrogen moves at a significant velocity, enabling excellent convective heat transfer between the shield and hydrogen. Parameters are reported in Table II.
- *Inside the cable*: inside gaps between the MgB₂ wires, liquid hydrogen is still present, but its velocity is near zero, leading to a thermal exchange where convection does not contribute significantly. Parameters are reported in Table III

TABLE II
HYDROGEN OUTSIDE THE CABLE

Property	Symbol	Value	Unit (SI)
Mass Flow Rate	\dot{m}	$1.389 \times 10^{+0}$	kg/s
Velocity	v	$1.114 \times 10^{+0}$	m/s
Fluid Area	S_h	1.809×10^{-2}	m ²
Wet Perimeter	P_{wet}	8.193×10^{-2}	m
Hydraulic Diameter	D_h	1.279×10^{-1}	m
Convective Coefficient	h	$1.604 \times 10^{+3}$	W/m ² /K

TABLE III
HYDROGEN INSIDE THE CABLE

Property	Symbol	Value	Unit (SI)
Velocity	v	≈ 0	m/s
Nusselt Number	Nu	1	—
Fluid Area	S_h	1.847×10^{-5}	m ²
Wet Perimeter	P_{wet}	1.698×10^{-1}	m
Hydraulic Diameter	D_h	4.350×10^{-4}	m
Convective Coefficient	h	$2.421 \times 10^{+2}$	W/m ² /K

In the following, the inner environment will be analyzed, to determine the heat exchange phenomena occurring inside the cable. Referring to Figure 8b, we observe that the former is in contact with the MgB₂ wires and, on part of its outer surface, it is also lapped by hydrogen. The MgB₂ wires, in turn, are exposed to liquid hydrogen, but they also make contact with the former and the carbon black. Thus, both the former and the MgB₂ conduct heat through both conduction and convection. This is also illustrated in Figure 7a, where with red single arrow is represented the conduction, while with the two yellow arrows is represented the convection heat exchange with the hydrogen. The three main types of heat transfer occurring within the cable are:

- Conduction through contact resistance between MgB₂ and the former.
- Conduction through the insulator between MgB₂ and the shield.

- Convection between the former, MgB₂, and the shield with the hydrogen inside the cable.

The following subsections provide a detailed examination for each of the thermal exchange mechanism.

1) *MgB₂ / Former*: To model the conduction between the former and MgB₂ wires, we started from experimental thermal contact conductance measurements reported in [26]. Since no measurements have been made between copper and monel, we referred to the thermal contact conductance between two copper surfaces pressed together with a force of 50 kg. In this study, thermal contact conductance across a one-square-centimeter surface was measured over a temperature range of 5 K to 40 K. It varied from 12.6 mW/K at the lower end to 70 mW/K at the higher end, with a specific value of 50 mW/K observed at the operational temperature of 23 K. Just as with the thermal contact conductance, the derived thermal conductivity will also be dependent on temperature.

Simulation packages as Simulink are usually only capable to model heat conduction through a material of surface S and thickness d . So it is needed to convert the contact conductance into the thermal conductivity of a fictitious material. For the thermal exchange surface, arcs of a circle were considered, thus we need to refer to the heat transfer formula for cylindrical geometry:

$$G_{th} = k_{th} \cdot \frac{2\pi}{\ln\left(\frac{r_o}{r_i}\right)} \cdot L \quad \left[\frac{W}{K}\right] \quad (4)$$

where r_o and r_i are the outer and inner radii, respectively, of the fictitious material, whose average radius corresponds to the radius of an MgB₂ wire. k_{th} is the thermal conductivity of the fictitious material that needs to be determined and L is the length.

Knowing that the relation between thermal conductance G_{th} and thermal contact conductance G_c is:

$$G_{th} = G_c \cdot 2\pi \frac{r_i + r_o}{2} L \quad \left[\frac{W}{K}\right] \quad (5)$$

where the factor that multiply G_c denotes the cylindrical surface with a radius equal to the average radius between r_i and r_o , and length L .

It is possible to equate (4) with (5) and derive the thermal conductivity:

$$k_{th} = G_c \cdot \left[\frac{r_i + r_o}{2} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{r_o}{r_i}\right)\right] \quad \left[\frac{W}{m \cdot K}\right] \quad (6)$$

Since Simulink compute the thermal conductance only through parameters present in (4), to account for conduction occurring only along arcs of a circle, we must incorporate these geometric factors into the thermal conductivity k_{th} . Looking at the Figure 8c, the assumption is that the MgB₂ wire is in contact with the former and with the carbon black (the orange and black horizontal rectangle) only for 1/9 of its circumference and with the adjacent wires with only 1/18 of it. These values were obtained by averaging the estimated contact area between each MgB₂ conductor and the former. So for the MgB₂-Former contact we obtain a fictitious thermal conductivity to implement in Simulink as:

$$k_{Sim} = N_{wires} \cdot S_{ratio} \cdot k_{th} = 36 \cdot \frac{1}{9} \cdot k_{th} \quad (7)$$

TABLE IV

COMPARISON BETWEEN THERMAL EXCHANGE COEFFICIENT (U) PER UNIT LENGTH FOR DIFFERENT MATERIAL PAIRINGS WITHIN THE CABLE.

Components	U (W/K)	Percentage
Former - MgB ₂	8.46	53.3%
Former - LH ₂ int	7.41	46.7%
Former - All	15.87	100.0%
MgB ₂ - LH ₂ int	24.28	73.6%
MgB ₂ - Former	8.46	25.7%
MgB ₂ - Shield	0.23	0.7%
MgB ₂ - All	32.97	100.0%
Shield - MgB ₂	0.23	0.2%
Shield - LH ₂ int	1.44	1.1%
Shield - LH ₂ ext	131.46	98.7%
Shield - All	133.13	100.0%
LH ₂ int - MgB ₂	24.28	73.3%
LH ₂ int - Former	7.41	22.4%
LH ₂ int - Shield	1.44	4.3%
LH ₂ int - All	33.13	100.0%

where N_{wires} is the number of MgB₂ wires and S_{ratio} is the ratio between the MgB₂ wires' circumference in contact and the total circumference.

2) *MgB₂ / Shield*: The thermal conductance through Polypropylene Laminated Paper (PPLP) insulation was calculated. This was followed by determining the conductance between the MgB₂ wires, which occurs solely through the contact surface via carbon black. The thermal resistances of these two components were then combined in series, resulting in a final thermal heat exchange coefficient between the MgB₂ wires and the shield through the insulation. It is noted that the thermal conductivity of PPLP is assumed to be 0.1 W/m/K at 23 K, as it is impregnated with liquid hydrogen, which also has a thermal conductivity of 0.1 W/m/K.

3) *LH₂int / Former, LH₂int / MgB₂, LH₂int / Shield*: To model the heat transfer between all the materials and the hydrogen present in the gaps between conductors, it was necessary to approximate a convective coefficient, which in turn depends on the hydraulic diameter. Determining the hydraulic diameter required first calculating the total cross-sectional area traversed by the fluid and the wetted perimeter, which is the actual surface of each material contacted by the fluid. Both the cross-sectional area traversed by the fluid and the wetted perimeter were determined through geometric approximations based on an empirical approach, considering Figure 8. Finally, the convective coefficient was determined considering a unit Nusselt number, indicating that convection has a negligible effect on heat transfer.

In summary, for the Concentric One Layer 36 MgB₂ wires cable, the following six thermal exchanges are present (also depicted in Figure 7a, with the same enumeration):

- 1) Former - MgB₂
- 2) Former - LH₂int
- 3) MgB₂ - Shield
- 4) MgB₂ - LH₂int
- 5) Shield - LH₂int
- 6) Shield - LH₂ext

For each of these thermal exchanges, a thermal exchange coefficient per unit length (U) has been determined between each pair of materials inside the cable. To better understand how heat transfer occurs within the cable, Table IV presents the heat flux per unit temperature difference and per unit length between each pair of materials for the Concentric One Layer 36 MgB₂ wires cable. The table is divided into sections, with each section representing the heat flux that would occur between one material and the others it contacts, assuming a temperature difference of 1K and 1m length. The columns show the absolute value of the heat flux and the percentage of the total heat flux exchanged by that particular material with others. It is crucial to highlight the distinction between *LH₂int*—hydrogen inside the cable with negligible velocity—and *LH₂ext*—hydrogen outside the cable, which moves more rapidly and thus has a significant convective heat transfer coefficient.

C. Power System Model

In all three simulation cases for the cable layouts, the external circuit of Figure 4 is utilized, where the fault occurs outside the cable on the load side.

As an external circuit, a system powered by two voltage generators was implemented, with a grounding between them to create a dual-monopole system at ± 25 kV. Each generator is connected in series with a DC Circuit Breaker (DCCB), the cable, and a load. The system also includes AC Circuit Breakers (ACCBs), which opens within 60 ms in the event of a failure of all downstream protections, resulting in the worst-case scenario [27]. However, the current in the two monopoles does not stop when the ACCBs open. This is due to the presence of the Modular Multilevel Converter (MMC). The converter is controlled under normal operation, but during a fault, the MMC turns off all its IGBTs, allowing current to freely circulate through the recirculation diodes in each submodule. The MMC parameters used in the simulation are reported in Table V. If the fault is a direct pole-to-pole type and the cable is still in the superconductive state, when ACCBs open, the only significant resistance is that of the diodes in the MMC, which determines the current decay time constant within the monopoles.

TABLE V
MMC PARAMETERS.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Number of arms	3	-
Number of submodules per arm	22	-
MMC arm Inductance	3.48	mH
MMC arm Capacity (equivalent)	650	μF
MMC arm resistance	22	$m\Omega$

V. RESULTS

This section presents the results from simulations of three different cable layouts. The characteristic times for each simulation are detailed in Table VI. Initially, the cables are

energized from 0 V to +25 kV by imposing a ramp increase in the generator voltage over a period of 1 second. At 10 s, a direct Pole-to-Pole fault occurs outside the cable and the ACCBs open to clear the fault within 60 ms. The simulation ends at 12 s.

TABLE VI
EVENTS' TIME IN SIMULATION

Property	Symbol	Value [s]
Start Energization	t_1	0.000
End Energization	t_2	1.000
Pole to Pole Fault	t_3	10.000
Open Breakers	t_4	10.060
End simulation	t_5	12.000

It should be noted that although in Section IV-A the former was modeled as divided into its concentric layers, the figures that follow depict only the total current of all former layers combined.

A. Energization

The cable is energized in all three configurations through a voltage ramp from 0 kV to +25 kV over a period of one second. As observed in all three graphs in Figure 9, the cable current reaches its nominal value after approximately 2 seconds for every configuration. What differs is the internal current distribution among the layers. As described in Section IV-A, only in the Concentric Two Layers 42MgB₂ wires cable, the superconducting wires are magnetically non-equivalent, as they lie on two different concentric layers that link different fluxes. In this case only, we expect the currents carried by the two layers to be significantly different. Indeed, referring to Figure 9c, it is evident that during the energization transient, the currents of the two layers are markedly nonuniform.

To understand the reasons behind this, it is important to remember that in superconductors, the distribution of current is primarily governed by inductive reactance rather than resistance. With this concept in mind, we can explain the observed behavior referring to Figure 10, where the currents of each layer (solid lines) and their respective critical currents (dashed lines) are depicted. At time $t = 0$ s both layers don't transport any current. However, their critical currents I_c differ because the internal layer contains 18 MgB₂ wires, while the external layer has 24 MgB₂ wires. As a result, the external layer has a higher critical current, assuming the temperature is the same and the magnetic field is zero due to the absence of current in both layers.

During energization, the two layers exhibit a pronounced skin effect, initially confining all the current to the outermost layer (MgB₂ 2). This condition persists until the current in this outer layer surpasses its critical current I_c at around 1 s. Subsequently, as the resistance of the outermost layer increases, the current begins to redistribute to the inner layer (MgB₂ 1). While the current in the outer layer stabilizes around its I_c value, the inner layer starts to carry only the excess current that surpasses the I_c of the outer layer. Another important characteristic superconducting cables exhibit is that,

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 9. Currents distribution among the cables' layers during the energization's ramp (0-25)kV in 1s. (a) Concentric One Layer 36 MgB₂ wires; (b) Rope-Strand 6 Petals 48 MgB₂ Wires; (c) Concentric Two Layers 42 MgB₂ Wires.

due to negligible resistance, which is solely attributable to joints and terminations, the time constant of a transient is extremely long. This can be observed in Figure 10, where even though the cable current reaches steady state after 2 s, the currents in the two layers are far from being evenly distributed even at 10 s.

B. Pole to Pole Fault

The graphs depicting the behavior of the three cable types during a fault are shown in Figure 11. For the reasons explained in IV-C, the total current of the cable, represented by

Fig. 10. Critical current and transport current of the two MgB₂ layers. In blue the innermost layer (MgB₂ 1). In magenta the outermost layer (MgB₂ 2).

the black dashed line, continues to circulate after the ACCBs open and decays with a certain time constant, diminishing to zero in about a second, due to the losses in the MMC's passive components. Since the converter powering the cable is the same in all three cases, and given that the converter has the most significant resistance, the time constant is very similar across all scenarios.

The shield, in all three cases, is grounded at both ends of the cable (solid grounded configuration) with a 1 Ω ground resistance. For this reason, during any fast transient, shield carries currents induced by the other layers.

Notably, in Figure 11a, the superconductor fails to carry the entire fault current, resulting in current sharing with the former. Since the former has a considerable cross-section, it is capable of carrying part of the fault current without overheating before the circuit breakers open the fault. Due to this characteristic, this layout is also called a *fault-resistant* cable.

It is valuable to take a moment to analyze more closely the current profile of the MgB₂ layer shown in Figure 11a. It is observed that immediately after the fault, there is a peak of 26 kA, then the current drops to 8.5 kA, and then there is another peak of 12 kA at 10.1 s. Let us provide an explanation for this particular behavior: The current distribution within the superconductor layer is governed by the parallel connection of:

- **The copper former**, whose resistivity remains almost constant during the fault.
- **The MgB₂ superconducting layer**, whose resistivity is highly nonlinear.

As shown at the two graphs of Figure 12, at 10 s, the current begins to increase, and the critical current in the superconductor is exceeded. This means that the resistivity of the superconducting wires increases exponentially, and the resistance of the MgB₂ layer becomes comparable to that of the former. This leads to current sharing, and the MgB₂ layer starts to offload its transport current on the former. At 10.06 s, the ACCBs disconnect the source to de-energize the fault. Now, the total current in the cable decreases following an exponential discharge trend. The current in the superconducting layer decreases until it falls below the critical current I_c . At this point, the electrical conductivity of the superconducting

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 11. Currents' distribution among the cables' layers during the pole to pole fault. (a) Concentric One Layer 36 MgB₂ wires; (b) Rope-Strand 6 Petals 48 MgB₂ Wires; (c) Concentric Two Layers 42 MgB₂ Wires.

layer increases sharply, and the current begins to redistribute, flowing from the former back to the MgB₂ wires. At 10.2 s, the former has completely offloaded its current, which is now entirely carried by the superconducting layer. This is excellent behavior, indicating that the cable can promptly recover its superconductive state as soon as the breakers clear the fault.

This type of current behavior in the superconductor depends on the magnetic field, temperature, and the current carried by the MgB₂ layer, making it extremely difficult to estimate a priori. Small variations in fault conditions or circuit configurations can lead to significantly different current profiles due to the strong non-linearity of the superconductor's resistivity.

Fig. 12. (a1) Zoom of Figure 11a in the time interval between 9.9 s and 10.2 s, excluding the shield current; (a2) Comparison between the current of the MgB₂ layer and its critical current I_c .

Considering the cable with two concentric layers, it presents the worst scenario even during a fault as we can see from Figure 11c and 13c. In fact, we have already noted that just before the fault, the outer layer carries a current similar to its I_c , and so it quenches as soon as the fault current begins to rise. Therefore, during its transition, the current is transferred to the inner layer, which also exceeds its critical current. As a result, the only remaining path for the current is through the former, which, in this configuration, possesses a significantly smaller cross-section than that observed in the single-layer case. Specifically, in the two-layer cable, the former comprises 19 copper conductors, whereas in the single-layer cable, there are 61 copper wires (see Figures 3c and 3a). The presence of so little copper causes the former to heat up significantly, as shown in Figure 13c, consequently heating both MgB₂ layers that wrap the former. Since the cable during the fault exhibits higher resistance, it is observed that the peak of the fault current is about 3 kA lower than in the case of the Rope-Strand 6 Petals 48 MgB₂ Wires. As previously mentioned, the Rope-Strand 6 Petals 48 MgB₂ Wires configuration is *fault transparent*, meaning that the superconductor within the cable can handle the entire fault current on its own. This prevents significant current sharing with the central former or the copper at the center of each petal. Consequently, there is no resistance introduced that would limit the fault current.

Finally, let's examine the temperatures shown in the graphs of Figure 13. We can observe that in the case of the single-layer cable, the MgB₂ temperature stays below 30K. In the "fault transparent" configuration, the temperature even stays below 25 K due to the higher number of MgB₂ wires that prevents the cable current from reaching the critical current under a 25 kA fault condition.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we explored three MgB₂ cable designs within the SCARLET project, detailing their structures and

Fig. 13. Temperature of each layer during the whole simulation. (a) Concentric One Layer 36 MgB₂ wires; (b) Rope-Strand 6 Petals 48 MgB₂ Wires; (c) Concentric Two Layers 42 MgB₂ Wires.

highlighting distinctive features. Through extensive electro-thermal simulations, these designs were assessed under various operational and fault conditions. We also introduced a detailed thermal model to better understand the thermal dynamics within these cables.

The simulation results reveal notable performance differences between the cable configurations. The multi-bundle petal configuration stands out as the best option, managing to fit a higher number of MgB₂ wires within a compact diameter that meets the SCARLET project's specifications. This design effectively keeps each wire within an acceptable magnetic field range, thus preserving the superconductor's performance.

On the other hand, the cable with two concentric layers of MgB_2 showed the poorest performance, particularly during fault conditions, due to complex current distribution and thermal management issues.

The single-layer MgB_2 cable configuration performed well in transient conditions, without showing any relevant issues. Furthermore, its concentric layout offers simpler construction compared to the multi-bundle design, and the more extensive supplier base offers better production reliability. Due to these reasons, the *single-layer 36 MgB_2 wires* layout presents the practical choice for the SCARLET project's demonstrator.

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